

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF SALT-FOG EXPOSURE ON THE PERFORMANCE AND RECYCLABILITY OF BIO-BASED EPOXY COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH NATURAL FIBRES

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Keywords: Polymer recycling, Bio-based composites, Thermosetting resins, Accelerated aging

ABSTRACT

This work aims to investigate the impact of salt-fog exposure on the mechanical performance and recyclability of flax fabric-reinforced bio-based epoxy resins, with the goal of assessing their suitability for marine environments. In such a context, three bio-based epoxy systems—Polar Bear, Green Turtle, and Plankton (having bio-carbon contents of 28–70%), were combined with recyclable (Recyclamine™ R*101) and non-recyclable hardeners to produce flax fibre-reinforced biocomposites. Before assessing the aging resistance of the composites, a preliminary investigation was conducted to identify the most promising bio-based epoxy systems based on a thorough assessment of their initial mechanical and thermal characteristics. This preliminary investigation showed that Polar Bear and Green Turtle systems demonstrated quite good mechanical and thermal properties, while Plankton with recyclable hardener exhibited incomplete curing and poor mechanical performance.

Subsequently, four biocomposites were manufactured using the vacuum infusion technique, with the pre-selected bio-based epoxy systems as polymeric matrices and bidirectional flax fabrics as reinforcement. To simulate the aggressive conditions of marine and coastal environments, mechanical tests were systematically conducted on fibre reinforced composite samples exposed to accelerated salt-fog aging up to 3 months. The evolution of the mechanical performance of biocomposites during aging was analysed through flexural and low-velocity impact tests.

Similarly to the mechanical characterization, an optimized recycling process was carried out on bio-based composites aged under salt-fog spray conditions for 30, 60, and 90 days, as well as on unaged samples as a reference.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today, fibre reinforced polymer materials (FRPs) are a cornerstone of modern industry. Their widespread adoption is due to the powerful combination of their reinforcement and matrix phases, which work together to deliver exceptional strength, stiffness, and durability without adding significant weight. On the other hand, these materials have a significant environmental impact, stemming from both the high energy consumption and environmental footprints associated with the extraction and synthesis of their raw materials (i.e., synthetic fibres and petroleum-based polymers) and the substantial challenges in their end-of-life management, especially for thermoset-based composites [1]. Rigid and cross-linked thermoset matrices make most FRPs difficult to reprocess and reuse [2].

Given the imperative to reduce carbon dioxide emissions and the finite nature of fossil resources, there is a global push for more sustainable materials. Consequently, the full or partial replacement of synthetic fibres with their natural counterparts represents a valid choice to mitigate the environmental impact of traditional FRPs [3, 4]. Furthermore, to comprehensively address this issue, attention must also be directed toward the matrix phase, given that the development and utilization of bio-based, recyclable and/or biodegradable polymer matrices are critical for eliminating the environmental impact of FRPs.

In this context, significant recent research has focused on bio-based polymers as environmentally friendly and economically viable alternatives to traditional petroleum-derived materials. Specifically, bio-based thermoset resins, partially derived from renewable resources like plant oils and lignin, are gaining traction as eco-friendly composite matrices [5]. These bio-based thermoset resins present a greener alternative to conventional epoxies, not only maintaining desirable mechanical properties and chemical resistance but also promising a reduced carbon footprint and less reliance on non-renewable resources, thereby aligning with a circular economy.

To further enhance sustainability, the recyclability and end-of-life management of bio-based epoxy composites are crucial research areas. Therefore, developing novel bio-based epoxy chemistries that allow for easier depolymerization or reprocessing without significant performance loss is a critical advancement. While thermal and mechanical recycling of fibre-reinforced composites have limitations, chemical recycling offers a promising alternative for recovering clean fibres and valuable monomers [6]. Cleavable amine-based epoxy systems, which allow for the recovery of thermoplastics and intact fibres under mild aqueous conditions, have shown technical and environmental effectiveness, though their long-term durability, especially with natural fibres, needs further investigation [7]. Due to these reasons, the present study comprehensively investigates the aging resistance of bio-based epoxy composites reinforced with flax fibres by evaluating their durability under harsh environment (i.e., salt-fog spray condition) also evaluating the impact of salt-fog exposure on durability of novel and potentially recyclable bio-based epoxy resins and their flax fibre reinforced composites.

Before assessing composite aging resistance, a preliminary investigation identified the most promising bio-based epoxy systems based on their initial mechanical and Thermal characteristics. Subsequently, four fibre-reinforced composites were manufactured through vacuum infusion technique, utilizing the pre-selected bio-based epoxy systems as polymeric matrices and bidirectional flax fabrics as reinforcement.

These composite materials were then exposed to salt-fog spray conditions for up to three months to assess the impact of this harsh environment on their mechanical performance and recyclability. For this purpose, a comprehensive mechanical characterization (including flexural tests, and low-velocity impact tests) was conducted on unaged samples (used as reference) and on samples aged for 30, 60, and 90 days. Similarly, following a preliminary optimization of the recycling process on unaged biocomposite samples, the recycling yield was investigated as function of the salt-fog exposure time.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Three bio-based epoxy monomers - Polar Bear, Green Turtle, and Plankton - supplied by R*Concept, were used in this work. In particular, the monomer Polar Bear, with a bio-carbon content exceeding 28%, was mixed with the recyclable hardener Recyclamine™ R101 (100:22 by weight). This system serves as a reference in this work because it was already studied recently by other authors regarding its recyclability and usability as a polymeric matrix for FRPs [8-10]. Its recyclability is attributed to Recyclamine, an amine-based hardener containing cleavable bonds within its structure. Specifically, this polyamine hardener, 2,2-Bis(aminoethoxy)propane, reacts with epoxy rings during curing to form acid-cleavable groups. These groups enable the recycling of epoxy thermosetting plastics and their composites. The process yields soluble monomeric or oligomeric products suitable for reuse, along with valuable fibres that retain their properties. The presence of these cleavable bonds allows the thermoset to transform into a thermoplastic polymer when crosslinks are broken via chemical treatment in an acetic acid solution [11-13].

The epoxy monomers Green Turtle (bio-carbon content >40%) and Plankton (bio-carbon content >77%) were each mixed with their non-recyclable hardeners (100:30 by weight) and with RecyclamineTM R101 (100:22 by weight) to obtain four additional epoxy systems.

Overall, five epoxy resins were initially evaluated for their mechanical and thermal properties. Mechanical tests involved three-point bending of five prismatic samples per resin (57.6 × 12.7 × 3 mm) using a Zwick-Roell Z005 machine (ASTM D790, 1.3 mm/min crosshead speed, 48 mm support span). Thermal behaviour was assessed via differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) on three 10 mg specimens per system using a Netzsch DSC 214 Polyma, heated from -20 °C to 210 °C at 10 °C/min under nitrogen flow.

After this preliminary comparison, the epoxy system obtained by mixing the Plankton monomer with the Recyclamine hardener was excluded from the subsequent biocomposite investigation due to its poor mechanical and thermal performance. Therefore, the remaining four epoxy systems were reinforced with six layers of flax balanced twill weave woven fabrics, supplied by Lineo, each having a nominal areal weight of 320 g/m². Rectangular panels (175 mm × 300 mm) were manufactured for each system using a vacuum infusion technique. The curing process involved an initial 24-hour cure at room temperature under vacuum, followed by post-curing. For the Polar Bear system, post-curing was conducted at 100 °C for 3 hours, while the Green Turtle and Plankton systems were post-cured at 80 °C for 4 hours. As indicated in Table 1, the investigated bio-based composites are coded F-PB-R, F-G-R, F-G-NR, and F-P-NR. 'F' denotes flax reinforcement, "PB", "G", and "P" represent Polar Bear, Green Turtle, and Plankton bio-based epoxy matrices, and "R" or "NR" indicate a recyclable (with Recyclamine) or non-recyclable epoxy matrix, respectively.

Composite	Nominal thickness [mm]	Fibre content [v/v%]	Experimental density [g/cm ³]	Theoretical density [g/cm ³]	Void content [v/v%]
F-PB-R	3.91	0.325	1.264	1.320	4.22
F-G-NR	4.01	0.317	1.252	1.309	4.31
F-P-NR	3.98	0.320	1.255	1.309	4.11
F-G-R	4.04	0.314	1.259	1.315	4.20

Table 1: Flax fibre-reinforced biocomposites.

2.1 Salt-fog spray aging conditions and characterization methods

The aging resistance of biocomposites was evaluated by exposing them to a salt-fog spray condition in a climate chamber (Ascott model CC1000IP) according to the ASTM B117 standard. Each panel was exposed to salt-spray fog (5 wt.% NaCl) at 35 °C ± 1°C for up to 3 months (90 days). A single set of specimens for mechanical characterization was removed from the climatic chamber and tested after 30, 60, and 90 days. Unaged specimens were also tested as a reference.

Three-point bending tests were conducted on prismatic specimens (80 mm × 17 mm) according to the ASTM D790 standard, using a Zwick-Roell Z005 universal testing machine. The span length and the crosshead speed were set to 64 mm and 1.7 mm/min, respectively

Low-velocity impacts were performed at room temperature with a 5 J energy level, using a 12.7 mm diameter hemispherical impactor weighing 3.05 kg. These impact tests were conducted using an Instron/Ceast 9340 instrumented drop-weight impact tower, following the ISO 6603-2 standard. For the tests, 7 cm × 7 cm square specimens were clamped between two steel plates, creating a 40 mm diameter circular unsupported area.

The morphology of the fractured surfaces of tensile samples was observed through a scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Quanta 450, USA).

The recycling process was applied to bio-based composites aged under salt-fog spray conditions for 30, 60, and 90 days, along with unaged reference samples. First, the recycling process was optimized on unaged composites made by Polar Bear resin. The selection of the optimum conditions for the recovery of thermoplastics was carried out starting from the methodology described by Saitta et al. [8]. Specifically, the variable parameters were the acetic acid concentration, the dissolution time, and the

ratio between the dissolved epoxy resin and acid. In a typical procedure, 10 g of epoxy resin were dissolved in an acetic acid solution (either 75% or 50% v/v) using resin-to-acid ratios of 1:30 or 1:20 (w/v). Dissolution was conducted at 80 °C for 90 or 180 minutes under constant mechanical stirring. After complete dissolution, flax fabrics were removed, washed in deionized water, and dried at 80 °C for 24 hours. The remaining solution was evaporated until its volume reached 75 mL. After cooling to 20 °C, it was neutralised with a 15% v/v ammonium hydroxide solution. The resulting precipitate was separated from the solution, washed with distilled water, and dried for 24 hours at 60 °C in a vacuum of 30 mbar. The optimal parameters and conditions for recycling the bio-based composite were finalised by evaluating recycling yield of the recovered thermoplastics.

The mass of recovered thermoplastics was taken into account to evaluate the recycling yield. The yield for the chemical recycling analyzed is determined by considering the Equation 1.

$$Yield (\%) = \frac{W_{initial}}{W_{product}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

where $W_{initial}$ and $W_{product}$ represent the mass of the initial epoxy resin in the composite sample and the mass of the thermoplastic obtained after recycling, respectively.

Beyond yield analysis, the recovered thermoplastic's thermal properties were assessed, with differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) used to determine its glass transition temperature (T_g). The polymer degradation temperature was determined as a peak on the DTG curve.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Bio-epoxy resins

Table 2 reports on the main mechanical and thermal properties of the bio-epoxy resins investigated. This preliminary investigation evidenced that all innovative systems (those obtained using Green Turtle or Plankton as bio-epoxy monomers) exhibit lower flexural strength and modulus, and higher deformation at break, compared to the reference (PB-R). Specifically, by mixing Plankton monomer (which has the highest bio-carbon content) with the recyclable hardener, dramatically decreases its flexural properties. In particular, the P-R epoxy system exhibits negligible strength and modulus values (2.0 MPa and 0.021 GPa, respectively), rendering it completely unsuitable as a polymeric matrix for biocomposites. Furthermore, the latter epoxy displayed a strain at break of 11.8%, a value notably higher than the typical range for fully cured thermoset polymers.

Composite	Flexural strength [MPa]	Flexural modulus [GPa]	Strain at break [%]	T_g [°C]
PB-R	97.6±8.1	2.8±0.2	4.1±0.7	67.9±0.2
G-NR	73.2±5.7	1.9±0.2	6.5±0.5	63.7±0.2
P-NR	83.9±3.7	2.8±0.1	4.9±0.1	76.3±0.2
G-R	39.9±0.6	1.1±0.02	7.9±0.2	31.0±0.2
P-R	2.0±0.2	0.02±0.004	11.8±1.3	18.6±0.3

Table 2: Mechanical and thermal properties of the bio-based epoxy resins.

Accordingly, calorimetric analysis showed that epoxy systems made with Green Turtle and Plankton monomers and non-recyclable hardeners (G-NR and P-NR) have glass transition temperatures (T_g) of 60 to 75 °C, similar to the reference system (PB-R). In contrast, using Recyclamine with either monomer significantly lowers the T_g values. Specifically, the P-R epoxy system shows a T_g of about 19 °C, much lower than typical room-temperature cured epoxy resins. These findings are likely due to an incomplete curing reaction between Recyclamine and the Plankton monomer, resulting in a thermoset structure with a relatively low cross-linking density. Indeed, the Plankton monomer is bisphenol-free, containing more than two epoxy rings in its chain. Consequently, it did not react properly with Recyclamine, which is designed to cure with DGEBA (such as Polar Bear and Green Turtle). Overall, the preliminary investigation indicated that this epoxy system is unsuitable as a composite matrix and will be excluded

from the subsequent phase of the work, which involves assessing biocomposites' performance during aging.

3.2 Bio-based epoxy composites

The flexural strength and modulus values of unaged bio-based composites are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Flexural strength and modulus of unaged biocomposites.

By observing these graphs, it is possible to notice that biocomposite made with the G-R epoxy resin (i.e., obtained by combining Green Turtle monomer with Recyclamine hardener) exhibited approximately half the flexural properties compared to other investigated biocomposites whereas biocomposites derived using standard epoxy resins (G-NR and P-NR) as matrix exhibited mechanical performance in their unaged state comparable to those manufactured with the reference epoxy matrix (PB-R). These results are in full agreement with observations for neat (i.e., unreinforced) polymeric epoxy systems.

The impact of salt-fog exposure on the flexural properties (strength and modulus) of the investigated biocomposites is displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Variation of (a) flexural strength and (b) modulus of aged biocomposites for different aging times.

First, it is worth noting that, despite their initial high flexural properties, F-PB-R, F-G-NR, and F-P-NR laminates exhibited poor aging resistance, with significant declines in mechanical stability after just 30 days of salt-fog exposure. During this initial aging period, the flexural strength and modulus of F-PB-R composites decreased by 28.3% and 52.1%, respectively. Even more pronounced, the F-G-NR and F-P-NR samples exhibited flexural strength reductions of 44.8% and 58.3%, respectively, while their flexural modulus decreased by 67.9% and 70.7%. On the other hand, the F-G-R laminates surprisingly exhibited the best stability against salt-fog, demonstrating only slight decrements in flexural strength and modulus (1.9% and 6.1%, respectively) compared to their initial values after 30 days of exposure.

All bio-based composites experienced reduced mechanical performance when salt-fog exposure was prolonged to 60 and 90 days (2 and 3 months). In particular, F-G-R samples not only retained their mechanical performance after the first month of aging but also exhibited only gradual declines in properties even after 60 and 90 days of salt-fog exposure. After 90 days, for instance, flexural strength and modulus showed reductions of only 29.5% and 49.6%, respectively, in comparison to unaged samples.

These results can be explained by considering that, regardless of the bio-epoxy resin matrix, the main degradative mechanism during aging was matrix plasticization rather than internal damage at the fibre-matrix interface. As clearly shown in Figure 3, this led to reduced composite stiffness and increased flexibility for all bio-based composites.

Figure 3: Variation of flexural strain at break of aged biocomposites for different aging times.

Specifically, F-PB-R, F-G-NR, and F-P-NR showed plasticization within the first 30 days of salt-fog exposure, whereas this phenomenon was time-delayed for F-G-R, which evidenced a noticeable strain at break increment in the last 30 days of aging.

Figure 4 includes the representative force-displacement curves related to the low-velocity impact (LVI) tests performed on unaged bio-based composites. The performance of the biocomposites in relation to impact energy is very similar. Indeed, all the curves are closed, meaning that no laminate penetration occurred, regardless of the matrix used and the aging condition. Furthermore, F-GT-R composites exhibit the worst initial impact properties, with the lowest maximum force. Conversely, biocomposites F-G-NR and F-P-NR show the best impact behaviour prior to salt-fog exposure.

Figure 4: Representative load-displacement curves for all unaged biocomposites obtained during low velocity impact tests.

The impact of aging on impact behaviour is characterized by main parameters from LVI tests, detailed in Table 3 as a function of salt-fog exposure time. These include maximum displacement (D_{max}) and damage degree (DD), calculated as the ratio of absorbed to impact energy (5 J).

Comparing the mechanical behaviour of biocomposites under low-velocity impact after salt-fog exposure, we notice that the impact performance of F-G-R composites was minimally affected by aging, consistent with quasi-static results. In contrast, salt-fog exposure proved particularly detrimental for Plankton-based composites (F-P-NR), leading to the most significant increases in damage.

Composite	F_{max} [N]	D_{max} [mm]	DD
F-PB-R	1891.5±30.1	3.6±0.1	0.76±0.01
F-PB-R_30	1942.3±68.6	4.1±0.2	0.78±0.02
F-PB-R_60	2187.9±95.1	3.7±0.1	0.76±0.01
F-PB-R_90	2018.4±67.5	4.1±0.2	0.78±0.02
F-G-NR	2105.4±31.4	3.2±0.1	0.77±0.01
F-G-NR_30	2088.8±36.4	3.6±0.1	0.78±0.01
F-G-NR_60	2041.7±62.2	3.7±0.1	0.82±0.01
F-G-NR_90	2091.9±23.7	3.7±0.1	0.79±0.01
F-P-NR	2198.9±57.6	3.1±0.1	0.72±0.01
F-P-NR_30	1834.3±22.7	4.1±0.1	0.81±0.01
F-P-NR_60	1990.8±87.5	3.7±0.2	0.79±0.02
F-P-NR_90	2248.5±33.8	4.1±0.1	0.80±0.01
F-G-R	1808.3±59.7	3.6±0.1	0.79±0.01
F-G-R_30	1854.1±20.6	4.3±0.1	0.82±0.01
F-G-R_60	1947.5±82.3	3.9±0.2	0.81±0.01
F-G-R_90	1920.7±69.7	3.8±0.1	0.82±0.01

Table 3: Main parameters obtained by LVI tests.

Overall, the data reported in Table 3 reveal that all bio-based composites exhibit increased maximum force, impactor displacement, and damage degree with increasing salt-fog exposure time. Furthermore, an overall decline in linear stiffness is observed during aging for all bio-based composites.

These results represent an indication of the augmented compliance shown by all biocomposites after aging. The greater absorbed energy with increased salt-fog exposure time confirms matrix plasticization as the main degradative phenomenon, which also plays a significant role in mitigating some internal damage due to a deterioration in interfacial adhesion, as corroborated by the post-impact analysis of sample surfaces. Indeed, observations of the impacted samples' front and back surfaces revealed that all biocomposites exhibited a significant reduction in indentation on the impacted face and crack severity on the opposite face after just 1-month aging. Figure 5 displays the impacted and opposing faces of only F-G-R samples before aging and after one month of salt-fog exposure. All biocomposites behaved similarly, and therefore, their related images are not included here for the sake of conciseness.

Figure 5: Observation of front and back surfaces of unaged and 1-month aged F-G-R biocomposites.

As concerns the recycling process, preliminary studies were conducted on the unaged F-PB-R composite samples. As detailed in Table 4, the investigation into the influence of chemical processing parameters—specifically acetic acid quantity, solution concentration, and dissolution time—demonstrated that a decrease in acid concentration from 75% to 50% correlated with a 32–65% reduction in product yield under consistent experimental conditions. The highest yield, 73.5%, was attained under optimum conditions: 200 ml of 75% v/v acetic acid and a dissolution time of 180 minutes. This indicates that peak yields necessitate high acidity and adequate dissolution time; conversely, diminished yields observed at 50% acidity and reduced dissolution periods are likely attributable to incomplete reaction kinetics and deviations from optimal pH levels. Furthermore, all recycled thermoplastic materials exhibited a glass transition temperature ranging from 73–82°C, indicating only slight variation based on recycling conditions. At lower acid concentrations (50% v/v), the T_g values were higher (~81°C), which may indicate lower cleavage of the cross-linked structures and reduced chain mobility. In contrast, samples processed under optimized conditions (75% v/v acetic acid, 200 mL, 180 min) showed the highest yield (73.5%) and a lower T_g (76.5°C), indicating a greater degree of depolymerization. These results demonstrate an inverse relationship between product yield and glass transition temperature, confirming that the use of high acid concentration and long reaction time effectively promotes efficient recycling.

Composite	Solution volume [mL]	Solution concentration [% v/v]	Dissolution time [min]	Recycling yield [%]	Glass transition temperature [°C]
F-PB-R	300	75	90	50.3	73.3
F-PB-R	300	75	180	34.2	75.6
F-PB-R	300	50	90	34.2	81.7
F-PB-R	300	50	180	34.9	79.4
F-PB-R	200	75	90	58.9	76.7
F-PB-R	200	75	180	73.5	76.5
F-PB-R	200	50	90	20.5	75.7
F-PB-R	200	50	180	25.1	81.1

Table 4: List of factorial experiments and main results for selecting optimal conditions for the recycling process.

In light of these findings, the optimized recycling conditions (200 mL solution volume, 75% v/v solution concentration, and 180 min dissolution time) were then employed to investigate the effect of aging on the efficiency of the bio-based composite. To this aim, recycling of both F-PB-R and F-GT-R samples was performed after 30, 60, and 90 days of salt-fog exposure.

As shown in Figure 6, the exposure to salt fog did not influence the recyclability of the biocomposites

to a high extent, regardless of the bio-epoxy resin used as matrix. Indeed, a slight increase in the recycling yield was found for both bio-based composites. Specifically, the unaged F-G-R sample exhibited an 80.7% thermoplastic yield under optimum conditions. This increased by about 4% to 84.7% after 90 days of aging in a climate chamber (F-G-R-90). On the other hand, the recycling yield of Polar Bear-based composites (F-PB-R) improved by 2.7%, from 73.5% (unaged sample) to 75.5% (90-day aged samples). Regarding the thermal behavior of the recycled material, limited reductions were observed in the glass transition temperatures for both bio-based epoxy resins across varying salt-fog exposure times.

Figure 6: Recycling yield and glass transition temperature values at varying salt-fog exposure.

Overall, these findings clearly demonstrate that the recyclability of the investigated bio-based composites was not negatively impacted by their exposure to aggressive environmental conditions, such as salt-fog. In fact, their ability to be recycled remained robust even after significant environmental stress, highlighting their potential for sustainable applications. It is worth noting that this represents an ongoing research activity. Further investigation will be conducted to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the recycled material's primary thermal and mechanical properties.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The experimental results demonstrate that all bio-based thermosetting composites exhibited satisfactory performance when subjected to aggressive conditions simulating a marine environment. Notably, both systems with lower bio-content can be recycled, unlike the one with the highest bio-content. These findings indicate that lower bio-content correlates with higher environmental resistance. Both reinforced recyclable epoxy composites (Polar Bear and Green Turtle) exhibited quite good mechanical strength with minimal loss of performance over several months of aging. In contrast, the Plankton-reinforced composites experienced a significant and progressive decline in performance over the same period. Consequently, the Green Turtle epoxy matrix emerges as the most suitable option, exhibiting high bio-content and recyclability, even after exposure to salt-fog spray condition. This combination positions it as a prime candidate to replace fossil-based epoxy resins, aligning with the principles of eco-sustainability and circular economy.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Funded by the European Union - Next Generation EU - PNRR M4 - C2 - investment 1.1: Fund for the National Research Program and Projects of Significant National Interest (PRIN) - PRIN 2022PNRR cod. P20223YBZ8_001 entitled "Recyclable biocomposites With eNanced Durability" (REWIND) CUP B53D23026710001.

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